

The Extraction Process and Optical Properties of Spinach and Teak Leaves for Dye Sensitized Solar Cell (DSSC)

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Abstract

Natural dyes of chlorophyll extract from spinach leaf and anthocyanin extract from teak leaf were used as sensitizer to fabricate dye sensitized solar cell (DSSC). They were extracted at different temperatures (30°C, 40°C and 50°C) and different solvents such as methanol and ethanol for 30 min, respectively. After extraction, chlorophyll and anthocyanin based solution (dyes) were formed. These dyes were investigated by UV-Vis spectroscopy. The absorption spectra of these dyes showed the optical properties like energy band gap. From absorption spectrum, the spinach dye with methanol solvent at 30°C for 30 min exhibited the maximum value of band gap energy (2.51eV) while the teak dye with methanol solvent at 50°C for 30 min also indicated the minimum degree of band gap energy (1.79eV).

Keywords: Dyes, sensitizer, Uv-Vis spectroscopy, DSSC.

I. Introduction

Dye-sensitized solar cell is a dye-based solar cell that converts light energy into electrical energy by using semiconductor materials that have the wide band gap. The dye-sensitized solar cell consists of the metal oxide semiconductor, photo anode, a dye sensitizer, an electrolyte and counter electrode. The dye sensitizer plays a key role in developing the high performance of DSSC. The efficiency of DSSC depends mainly on its properties such as the absorption spectrum. The dye, photosensitizers, plays an important role is absorbing sunlight and transporting electrons into the conduction band of the semiconductor, converting the energy from sunlight into electricity with photovoltaic effects in DSSC.

Natural dye is easy to obtain and the cost is very low. Green plants are mostly rich in chlorophyll and red leaves are rich in anthocyanin. Natural dyes extracted from plants, fruits and flower contains pigments such as anthocyanin, chlorophyll, etc. Chlorophyll pigments can be used as a dye sensitizer in DSSC because of its ability in absorbing photon from sunlight. Chlorophyll exhibits two main absorption peaks in the visible region at the wavelengths of 427 and 660 nm. Anthocyanin is a pigment, that this is red, blue and purple on the fruits, flowers and leaves. Anthocyanin shows absorbance spectrum in the visible range (450-580nm). In this research work, Spinach (*Spinacia oleracea*) and teak (*Tectona grandis*) with different temperature are prepared by extraction with ethanol and methanol solvents. The optical properties of the prepared dye solution are characterized by UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy.

II. Preparation of Dyes Solution

The spinach leaves and teak leaves were collected from the Bago Township. The collected leaves were washed with pure water to remove the dust and other impurities. These leaves were spread in a shade for three days under room temperature to dry out the water content in the leaves. They were cut into smaller pieces and grinded with motor. The solvents used in extracting dye from spinach leaves and teak leaves were methanol and ethanol, respectively.

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5 g of spinach leaves and teak leaves were weighed by digital balance and put them into the beaker. And they were mixed with 100ml of methanol and ethanol. These solutions were stirred with magnetic stirrer at different temperatures (30°C, 40°C and 50°C) for 30 min. Spinach and teak dye solutions were obtained and cooled down at room temperature. The dye solutions were filtered with filter paper. Finally, the extracted dye solutions were put into sample tube. Chlorophyll dye was extracted from spinach leaves and anthocyanin dye was extracted from teak leaves. The optical properties of these natural dyes were characterized by UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy. Optical characteristic of dye solution was examined in the wavelength range from 190 nm to 1100nm using UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy.

Fig(1) Block Diagram of Experimental Procedure for Natural Dye Extraction

III. Results and Discussion

In semiconductor physics, the band gap of a semiconductor was calculated by two types of method: direct method and Tauc method. The variation of band gap energy for the spinach and teak dye with ethanol and methanol solvents at 30°C, 40°C and 50°C for 30 min were calculated by direct and Tauc method.

Direct Method

The energy of the photon ($E = h\nu = \frac{hc}{\lambda}$; where E = energy, h = Planck's constant, ν = frequency of light, c = speed of light, and λ = wavelength of light) is directly related to the band gap size. The energy of the band gap is inversely proportional to the wavelength of light. The greater the band gap energy, the smaller the wavelength.

Tauc Method

The band gaps can be calculated via UV-Vis spectroscopy using Tauc Plots. The graph is between $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ on y-axis and $h\nu$ on x-axis. The absorbance can be calculated from UV and $h\nu$ can be calculated by following way $h\nu = \frac{1240}{\lambda}$. Band gap energy can be calculated by extrapolating the vertical segments of plot to intersect on x-axis where y-axis is zero. And then the value of band gap energy can be obtained by Tauc method.

Fig (2) (a), (b) and (c) showed the UV-Vis absorption spectrum and $(\alpha h\nu)^2 - h\nu$ characteristic of spinach dye extracted with ethanol at temperature 30°C, 40°C and 50°C for 30 min. The absorption peak of spinach dye extracted with ethanol could be seen at a wavelength between 510 nm and 525 nm. Fig (3) (a), (b) and (c) indicated the UV-Vis absorption spectrum and $(\alpha h\nu)^2 - h\nu$ characteristic of spinach dye extracted with methanol at temperature 30°C, 40°C and 50°C for 30 min. The absorption peak of this dye extracted with methanol could be seen at a wavelength between 515 nm and 520 nm. Fig (4) (a), (b) and (c) showed the absorption spectrum and $(\alpha h\nu)^2 - h\nu$ characteristic of teak dye extracted with ethanol at temperature 30°C, 40°C and 50°C for 30 min. The absorption peak was a wavelength between 630 and 640 nm. Fig (5) (a), (b) and (c) showed the absorption spectrum and $(\alpha h\nu)^2 - h\nu$ characteristic of teak dye extracted with ethanol at temperature 30°C, 40°C and 50°C for 30 min. The absorption peak was a wavelength between 630 and 635 nm.

Table 1 and 2 showed the variation of band gap energy for spinach dye with ethanol and methanol at 30°C, 40°C and 50°C calculated by direct method ($E = hc/\lambda$) and Tauc method. Table 3 and 4 revealed the variation of band gap energy for teak dye with ethanol and methanol solvents at 30°C, 40°C and 50°C for 30 min were calculated by direct and Tauc method.

Fig 2 (a), (b) and (c) $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ and $h\nu$ Characteristics Curve for Spinach Solution with Ethanol Solvent at 30°C, 40°C and 50°C for 30 min

Fig3 (a), (b) and (c) $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ and $h\nu$ Characteristics Curve for Spinach Solution with Methanol Solvent at 30°C, 40°C and 50°C for 30 min

Fig4 (a), (b) and (c) $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ and $h\nu$ Characteristics Curve for Teak Solution with Ethanol Solvent at 30°C, 40°C and 50°C for 30 min

Fig5 (a), (b) and (c) $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ and $h\nu$ Characteristics Curve for Teak Solution with Methanol Solvent at 30°C, 40°C and 50°C for 30 min

Table 1. Band Gap Energy at Different Temperatures (30°C, 40°C and 50°C) for Spinach Dye Solution with Ethanol Solvent Calculated by Direct and Tauc Method.

Temperature (°C)	Peak wavelength (nm)	Cut off wave-length (nm)	Energy band gap(eV) By Direct Method	Energy band gap (eV) By Tauc Method
30	650	510	2.42	2.5
40	647	520	2.37	2.49
50	647	525	2.35	2.47

Table 2. Band Gap Energy at Different Temperatures (30°C, 40°C and 50°C) for Spinach Dye Solution with Methanol Solvent Calculated by Direct and Tauc Method.

Temperature(°C)	Peak-wavelength (nm)	Cut off wave length (nm)	Energy band gap (eV) By Direct Method	Energy band gap (eV) By Tauc Method
30	648	515	2.42	2.51
40	648	524	2.37	2.48
50	648	520	2.35	2.46

Table 3. Band Gap Energy at Different Temperatures (30°C, 40°C and 50°C) for Teak Dye Solution with Ethanol Solvent Calculated by Direct and Tauc Method.

Temperature(°C)	Peak wavelengt(nm)	Cut off wave-length (nm)	Energy band gap (eV) By Direct Method	Energy band gap (eV) By Tauc Method
30	649	640	2.42	1.81
40	648	630	2.37	1.79
50	648	635	2.35	1.8

Table 4. Band Gap Energy at Different Temperatures (30°C, 40°C and 50°C) for Teak Dye Solution with Methanol Solvent Calculated by Direct Method.

Temperature(°C)	Peak-wavelength(nm)	Cut off wave length (nm)	Energy band gap(eV) By Direct Method	Energy band gap(eV) By Tauc Method
30	648	630	2.42	1.81
40	648	633	2.37	1.79
50	647	635	2.35	1.79

IV. Conclusion

The optical properties of spinach and teak extracted with different solvents at different temperature (30°C, 40°C and 50°C) have been investigated. In this work, the band gap energy of natural dyes is observed by two methods such as direct and Tauc methods. The widest band gap energy for spinach dye with ethanol solvent is observed at 30°C (2.5eV), with methanol solvent at 30°C (2.51 eV). In that case, the extracted spinach dye with methanol at 30°C gives the widest band gap energy. Meanwhile the smallest band gap energy for spinach dye with methanol at 50°C is found to be 2.46 eV. Teak dye with ethanol and methanol solvent at 30°C are observed as the most band gap energy as 1.81 eV. The least band gap energy for teak dye is 1.79 eV with methanol at 50°C. Overall, spinach dye with methanol solvent at 30°C is exhibited the maximum value of band gap energy (2.51eV) while the minimum degree of band gap energy (1.79eV) is formed for teak dye with methanol at 50°C. According to the results, the technique employs in this work is an uncomplicated way. From the experimental result of this research is credible and suitable for use in sensitizer of dye sensitized solar cell (DSSC).

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